

3D Printing of Antibacterial Nanoclay/Cellulose Composites for Regenerative Medicine

Üç Boyutlu Baskılı Antibakteriyel Nanokil/Selüloz Kompozitlerin Rejeneratif Tıpta Kullanımı

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ABSTRACT

The use of nanoscale materials allowed researchers to study a variety of disease treatments using minimally invasive techniques. Especially, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are of interest in biosensors and biomedical applications because they are nanoscale and have antibacterial properties. Although there are many production methods of nanoparticles, green approaches have been preferred in recent years as sustainability is a common concern with biological or bio based production and can produce fast, non-toxic and well-defined size and morphology. For wound dressing and wearable sensors, biopolymer cellulose-based films have promising advantages from conductivity to encapsulation of AgNPs within a cellulosic matrix. Reducing the inherent toxicity of AgNPs is essential in clinical uses; therefore, nanoclay composites can also be recommended. Clay nanomaterials as a naturally biocompatible atomically thin layered charged fine-grained structure, 2D for bioactive material and biomaterials. It has been used since 2500 years. The aim of this study is to present the development of regenerative medicine that combines antibacterial composite using AgNPs- nanoclay into cellulose polymer matrix with 3D printing. This review also covers green synthesis of AgNPs nanoparticles with the least amount of environmental damage with popular native herbs of Turkey AgNO₃ as a precursor. In the second part of the paper, cellulose structures and their bio-ink composites were also discussed. Finally, 3D assisted antibacterial composites demonstrated here is a viable option for antibacterial composite for regenerative medicine and wearable sensor science.

Keywords: Alginate, Ag-NPs, Antibacterial, Nanoclay, Regenerative medicine

ÖZET

Nano ölçekli malzemelerin kullanımı, araştırmacıların minimal invaziv teknikler kullanarak çeşitli hastalık tedavilerini incelemelerine izin vermektedir. Özellikle gümüş nanopartiküller (AgNP'ler), nanoboyutta olmaları ve antibakteriyel özelliklere sahip olmaları nedeniyle biyosensörlerde ve biyomedikal uygulamalarda ilgi görmektedir. Nanopartiküllerin pek çok üretim yöntemi olmasına rağmen, son yıllarda yeşil yaklaşımlar, sürdürülebilirliğin biyolojik veya biyobazlı üretimle ilgili ortak bir endişe olması ve hızlı, toksik olmaması ve iyi tanımlanmış boyut ve morfoloji üretebilmesi nedeniyle tercih edilmektedir. Yara sargısı ve giyilebilir sensörler için, biyopolimer selüloz bazlı filmler, iletkenlikten AgNP'lerin selülozik bir matris içinde kapsüllenmesine kadar umut verici avantajlara sahiptir. AgNP'lerin doğal toksisitesinin azaltılması, klinik kullanımlarda gereklidir; bu nedenle nanokil kompozitler önerilebilir. Doğal biyoyumlu atomik olarak ince katmanlı yüklü ince taneli yapı olarak kil nanomalzemeler, 2B biyoaktif madde ve biyomalzemeler için M.Ö. 2500'li yıllardan beri kullanılmaktadır. Bu çalışmanın amacı, rejeneratif tıp uygulamalarına yönelik olarak geliştirilen antibakteriyel AgNPs-nanokil katkılı sellüloz kompozitlerini incelemek ve 3B yazdırma konusundaki gelişmeleri sunmaktır. İlk bölümde gümüş nanopartiküllerinin yeşil sentezine ve kullanılan yerli bitkilere yer verilmiştir. Makalenin ikinci bölümünde, sellüloz yapıları ve onların

biyo-mürekkep kompozitleri ele alınmıştır. Son olarak, burada gösterilen 3B yardımcı antibakteriyel kompozitler, regeneratif tıp ve taşınabilir sensör biliminde giderek yaygınlaştığı, antibakteriyel kompozit olarak uygun bir seçenek olduğu kabul edilebilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ag-NPs, Alginat, Antibakteriyel, Nanokil, Regeneratif Tıp

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, several natural biopolymers, such as chitosan, collagen, gelatin, and cellulose, have been isolated. These substances carry the potential for use in a range of flexible devices like flexible sensors (Ling et al., 2018). Since it is a material that is renewable, sustainable, eco-friendly, and biocompatible, cellulose, one of the most abundant substances on earth, has recently attracted a lot of attention in a variety of technological applications (Anon n.d.-f, Anon n.d.-f; Bahloul et al., 2021; Mateo et al., 2021; Trache, 2018; Wang et al., 2019).

Cellulose and its derivatives are commonly known as eco-friendly and biocompatible polysaccharides, more than well-known polymers like chitosan, starch, and alginate. These unique cellulose structures have been utilized to create high-performing composites and are widely utilized in various industrial and biomedical applications, including drug delivery (Abou-Yousef et al., 2021), wound dressing coatings, superabsorbent, hydrogels (Mohd Zuki et al., 2018) and adsorbents, replacing commercial alternatives (Lin and Dufresne, 2014; Nasrollahzadeh et al. 2021; Seddiqi et al., 2021). Inexpensive and inventive composites can be created using cellulose derivatives. Additionally, cellulose offers significant benefits in addressing disposal and microplastic pollution issues (Janaswamy et al., 2022). From the mid-19th century, modified cellulose structures were made by adding metal ions to solutions of cellulose and metal salts, in order to preserve timbers (Anon n.d.-a). However, these altered cellulose structures have become highly appealing for a variety of uses, such as sensors, wearables, catalysts, and biomedicine.

Figure 1. An overlook to applications of Cellulose-based composites

Regenerative medicine aims to restore damaged or lost tissues and organs to improve quality of life. Noninvasive regenerative medicine is a field that utilizes minimally invasive techniques to achieve this goal (Friedrich et al., 2021a). Nanotechnological developments gives many promising

opportunities using nanoscale materials (Friedrich et al., 2021b). Last two decades, several nanotechnological approaches to biomedical area were developed. Among many nanoparticles, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have emerged as a promising material in this field due to their unique properties such as biocompatibility, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial effects. AgNPs have been used for wound healing, tissue engineering, and drug delivery applications. For instance, studies have shown that AgNPs can enhance the proliferation and migration of skin cells in wound healing (Vyavahare et al., 2021) and improve the mechanical and thermal properties of scaffolds for tissue engineering. For instance, the microstructures mimic the tissues behaviors and features therefor promoting cell adhesion and proliferation (Choudhury et al., 2020; Umair Wani et al., 2023). The use of AgNPs in noninvasive regenerative medicine offers a potential solution for improving patient outcomes and quality of life. The incorporation of AgNPs into wound dressings has been shown to improve their antibacterial activity. AgNPs have inherent antimicrobial properties due to the release of silver ions, which disrupt the cell membrane and metabolism of bacteria. This makes AgNPs a useful additive in wound dressings, where controlling bacterial infection is crucial for successful wound healing. Studies have demonstrated that the presence of AgNPs in wound dressings, even only silver in ionic form, can effectively inhibit the growth of various pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Benli and Yalın 2017; Palanisamy et al., 2014; Sheikh et al., 2009). Furthermore, the sustained release of silver ions from AgNPs can provide long-term antibacterial protection for the wound, even after the dressing is removed (Yang et al., 2012). However, long-term sustainability and their AgNPs toxicity is still a concern. In this regard, use of AgNPs in wound dressings can therefore improve the wound healing outcome by reducing the risk of bacterial infections.

Nanoclays are derived from clay minerals and known as popular multifunctional filler or additive due to many important characteristics of low toxicity and high biocompatibility. High aspect ratio, potentially exfoliation cause to high surface area and better adsorption properties (Majid et al., 2020; Singer et al., 2011). Therefore, clay minerals could be easily modified and functionalized their surfaces by polymers and could be improve the compatible nanocomposite structures after incorporation into polymer matrices (Benli et al., 2011; Günister et al., 2007).

Many review studies could be seen on cellulose-based inorganics, such as functional and sustainable sensing devices (Gabielli and Frascioni, 2022), medical diagnosis biosensors (Kamel and Khattab, 2020), coatings for textile and paper (Spagnuolo et al., 2022) and also as bio-derived fillers (Bahloul et al., 2021) and etc. Despite the numerous potential applications of cellulose and silver composites, there has been a limited amount of research in this area in recent literature. This presents a unique opportunity to explore the many benefits of cellulose through the creation of novel cellulose and silver nanoparticle composites. By examining the feasibility of silver/nanoclay antibacterial composites and conducting a comprehensive review of the recent developments in cellulose/silver composites, we aim to shed light on the limitless possibilities of cellulose in modern applications. First, the common preparation techniques were discussed, then silver nanoparticle synthesis and nanoclay preparation were reviewed. Finally, this review will conclude with the recent developments in 3D printing medicine bio-ink technology and future expectations of antibacterial cellulose composites.

2. CELLULOSE AND DERIVATIVES

Cellulose is considered as an attractive, macromolecule biopolymer for many applications. One of the most common materials on earth, cellulose has recently attracted a lot of attention from the technological applications since it is biocompatible, renewable, sustainable, and eco-friendly (Anon n.d.-f; Piantanida et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2019). Cellulose is known as an ideal material for biosensing and film patch designing due to its fascinating properties like; flexible surface chemistry (Vignesh et al., 2022), biocompatibility (Bahloul et al., 2021), renewability (Trache, 2018), biodegradability (Mateo et al., 2021). Firstly, cellulose is an important element of a

plant tissue which it has a linear structure. It is compound of D-anhydroglucopyranose units (AGUs), connected by β -glycosidic bonds (Anon n.d.-e). (Fig.1) Cellulose is a versatile, renewable and biocompatible polymer that has been widely utilized in various fields due to its exceptional properties. Derived from natural resources such as wood and cotton, cellulose and its derivatives have been used in industries ranging from paper and textiles to pharmaceuticals and biomedicine. These biopolymers possess excellent mechanical strength, high thermal stability, biodegradability and low toxicity, making them ideal for a wide range of applications. The unique structure of cellulose and its derivatives has also been leveraged to create high-performance composites, further expanding its potential uses. The continued exploration and development of cellulose and its derivatives is poised to have a significant impact on numerous industries, as it offers a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to traditional synthetic materials. As seen in Figure 2, Cellulose can be produced from plants and also alternative non-plant sources like bacteria or tunicate as the only cellulose producing animal. However, function of cellulose in animals and bacterial cells is different (Anon n.d.-j; Hasanin, 2022).

Figure 2. Cellulose sources and the flow chart of different production methods

3. SILVER NANOPARTICLES FORMS USING BY GREEN SYNTHESIS

Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have been widely studied for their potential use in various applications, including antimicrobial coatings, medical devices, and food packaging. These nanoparticles have outstanding antibacterial qualities and functions effectively against variety of bacteria, including gram-positive like *S. aureus* and gram-negative *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, and also drug-resistant bacteria (Guzman et al.,2012). Due to the significant environmental harm caused by nanomaterials created using traditional physicochemical methods, green synthesis techniques have to be developed in order to produce nanoparticles at a low cost of damage to natural habitats. Because they contain amino acids, flavonoids, aldehydes, ketones, amines, carboxylic acids, phenols, and protein, plant-based extracts have been a potential substitute to take into account. These substances have the ability to supply electrons that behave as reducing agents in the synthesis of nanoparticles. The metallic ions are reduced by the application of reducing agents, which supply electrons. Figure 3 shows the main reduction mechanism schematically.

Figure 3. Schematic representation for green synthesis of silver nanoparticles with plant extraction.

3.1. Herbs for green synthesis

Several herbs are used in the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles, Table 1 includes some of the most common of them. Nanoparticles can be stabilized by the addition of capping agents, preventing aggregation by attributing repulsive forces that influence the growth of nanoparticles (De Souza et al., 2019). These herbs contain natural reducing agents that help in the reduction of silver ions to form silver nanoparticles. The use of herbs in the synthesis of silver nanoparticles provides a safe and environmentally friendly alternative to the traditional chemical reduction methods. Additionally, the presence of functional groups in these herbs contributes to the stability and biocompatibility of the resulting silver nanoparticles.

Encapsulation of AgNPs within a cellulosic matrix can provide a safe and effective way to deliver these nanoparticles for such applications. This essay will discuss the modifications and encapsulation of AgNPs within cellulosic matrices and their potential for antibacterial activity. However, the problem of silver nanoparticles agglomerating in aqueous form can be overcome with the addition of polymers as stabilizing agents as well. The study of polymers such as alginate, chitosan, PVA and PVP in cooperation with silver nanoparticles for their use in the biomedical field is extensive. Alginate, which is a natural polymer extracted from brown algae, is known to form hydrogels with cations that have a valence of two, like Ca^{+2} , in its aqueous form through crosslinking. This hydrophilic, biocompatible and biodegradable gels shape can easily be manipulated which makes it useful not only in biomedicine but also in drug release, wound dressings, food industry and more (Armentano et al., 2013). The catalytic property and diffusion of silver nanoparticles can be advanced by taking advantage of high surface areas and channels of porous materials that can be effortlessly entered.

Table 1. Synthesis of metal nanoparticles using plant extract.

Plant Species	Used part	Product	Ref.
Neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>)	Leaf	Ag ZnO	(Iqbal et al., 2021)
Turmeric (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Rhizome	Ag	(Venkatadri et al., 2020)
Aloe vera	Leaf	Ag	(Anju et al., 2021)
Ginger (<i>Zingiber officinale</i>)	Rhizome	Ag Cu	Anon n.d.-d; Hu et al., 2022
Holy basil (<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>)	Leaf	Ag TiO ₂ ZnO	Ahmad et al., 2022; Baruah et al., 2021; Elsamra et al., 2023
Rosemary (<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>)	Flower, Leaf	MgO Au	Anon n.d.-j; Onmaz et al., 2022
Sage (<i>Salvia officinalis</i>)	Leaf	Ag ZnO	Abomuti et al., 2021; Sehna et al., 2019
Thyme (<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>)	Leaf (essential oil or waste)	Ag ZnO	Anon n.d.-i; Vinicius de Oliveira Brisola Maciel et al., 2020
Mint (<i>Mentha spicata</i>)	Leaf	ZnO Ag	(Abdelkhalik and Al-Askar, 2020; Ashrafi et al., 2022; Fatema et al., 2021)
Cinnamon (<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>)	Leaf, Bark	ZnO Pd Mn	Anon n.d.-e; Ansari et al., 2020; Kamran et al., 2019
Brassica Oleracea	Fruit Leaves	Ag	Tamileswari et al., 2015
Eucalyptus Oleosa	Leaf	Ag	Pourmortazavi et al., 2015
Ipomoea pes-caprae	Leaf	Ag	Kaliamurthi et al., 2013
Cumin	Seed	Ag Au	Choudhary et al., 2018
Punica Granatum	Fruit peel	Cu	Anon n.d.-b

4. NANOCLAY AND NANOSCALE PREPARATION

In this concept, when it comes to porous and biocompatible materials with high surface area, one of the first and preferred additive that comes to mind is. Nanoclays are natural or synthetically prepared nanoscale dispersed phyllosilicates. They are composed of layered silicates, with a thickness of only a few nanometers and a lateral dimension of several hundred nanometers (Villanueva et al., 2009). Clays, solid porous materials, can diminish the agglomeration issues, scatter different nanoparticles of active phases by becoming the active or passive supporting media. Its special acidity of surface, thermal stability is one of the reasons why clay supported nanoparticles are sought after in industrial applications (Luque and Varma, 2012). Figure 5 shows clay mineral as active agent vehicle and nanofiller in fabricating ceramic-polymer scaffolds for regenerative tissue and wound healing (Same et al., 2022).

Kaolin, montmorillonite (which is commonly referred to as bentonite as it accounts for over 90% of MMT), sepiolite, and zeolite are well-known types of clay minerals that have been extensively used in the production of polymeric nanocomposites. Despite their different chemical compositions and nanoparticle morphologies, all these clays are primarily composed of silicon and oxygen arranged in SiO₄ tetrahedral layers. They also commonly contain metallic exchange groups such as Na, Ca,

K, and Fe in thin octahedral sheets, with aluminum being the most prevalent in tetrahedral-based layers (Fu and Qutubuddin, 2000). Historically, metal ions have been widely employed as effective antimicrobial agents, with silver and copper being the most frequently used agents for the development of antimicrobial coatings. However, long-term sustainability can be an issue with these coatings due to the tendency of metal-ion-exchanged coatings to oxidize and lose their antimicrobial properties. Therefore, for these coatings to function efficiently, they must be able to penetrate the structural cavities and micropores of matrices, such as those found in palygorskite, zeolite, and Sep. This enables the metal ions to be firmly embedded within the matrix and remain active over time (Demirci et al., 2014). The anisotropic surfaces of raw Sep fibers, including ribbons, channels, and nano-sized tunnel pores, have been demonstrated through preliminary molecular dynamics simulations. These hydrophobic and hydrophilic ribbons offer new active adsorption sites after being well-dispersed in water. (Same et al., 2022). Benli et al. (2018) has shown that the matrix's release of Mg^{2+} ions is responsible for the viscoelastic behavior, hydrogen bonding, and improved cation exchange performance of clay. Kara et al. (2003) have previously detailed the mechanisms of cation exchange, including Co^{2+} . The adsorption efficiency sequence of Mg-enriched sepiolite has been found to be $Pb < Cd < Co < Zn < Cu$ (Brigatti et al., 2000), and $Ni < Cd < Zn$ (Helios-Rybicka 1985). Additionally, metal ions bound to the ribbons can improve the electrostatic attraction between negatively charged bacteria and sepiolite surfaces, thus enhancing its antibacterial properties in a manner similar to montmorillonite (Benli and Yalın, 2017).

Figure 5. Schematic process of utilizing clay mineral as active agent vehicle and nanofiller in fabricating ceramic-polymer scaffolds for regenerative tissue and wound healing (Same et al., 2022).

4.1 Nanoscale Processing Methods of Clays

Following the classical steps for processing natural clay minerals, grinding typically takes place after crushing and is commonly a wet process. The dispersion process refers to the deagglomeration and distribution of nanolayers within matrices or solvents. Nanofibers or nanoclay sheets/layers tend to aggregate due to attractive forces such as Van der Waals, which require stronger forces than inter-particle adhesion forces to overcome. Dispersion can occur through either the splitting up of agglomerates into small fragments under high stress (rupture) or the continuous detachment of small fragments at a lower stress (erosion). While water is typically used as a carrier for dispersing nanolayers/fibers, other chemical and physical treatments are employed to overcome agglomeration and entanglement (Benli and Yalın, 2017). The objective of clay mineral modification methods is to increase the number of adsorption sites and functional groups on their surfaces. To achieve high

efficiency as an adsorbent, the selection of an appropriate modifier is a crucial factor. This is because modifying the clay mineral leads to an increase in specific surface area, pore volume, and the number of surface acid sites. One convenient method of modifying clay minerals to change their surfaces from hydrophilic to hydrophobic is through the use of surfactants (Barakan and Aghazadeh, 2021). Although classical methods such as acid activation and thermal treatments are available, they can potentially damage the surfaces of clay minerals and require careful consideration. Acid treatments involve the intercalation of protons between the interlayer spaces of the clay, resulting in some damage to the silicate layer and partial dissolution of octahedral layer cations (Komadel and Madejová 2006). The physical characteristics of clay, such as its shape, size, porosity, amorphization, and crystallization, can be altered through thermal treatments (Bergaya and Lagaly, 2006). In addition, a method known as pillarization can be employed for Na-activated clays. This process involves an exchange reaction between the interlayer space and the polyoxycations present in the pillaring solution, followed by a calcination process to form stable pillars for catalytic activity (Vicente and Bergaya, 2013). Recently, ultrasonication is a commonly used disruptive force in laboratory-scale applications. However, for industrial-scale dispersion, media milling is a more common technique, which involves the use of micron-sized beads as grinding media to achieve the dispersion of nano-order particles. In order to achieve multifunctional functionalization of clay minerals, metal oxide impregnation and nanoparticle addition structures are increasingly being suggested (Benli and Gönül, 2021).

5. 3D PRINTING IN REGENERATIVE MEDICINE

3D printing has revolutionized the way we approach the development of new materials and devices, particularly in the field of medicine and wearable sensors. Extrusion based, inkjet based and laser assisted types of 3D printing are also possible (Figure 6). Using these technique layer by layer, tissue and/or organs could be possible and named as bioprinting. Development of bio-inks in essential for different applications since there are different aspects to be considered. To name some;

1. Viscosity: the bio-ink should be fluid during and solid after dispensing.
2. Gelatin process and stabilization: the resolution and viability of printed structure depends on the process of forming solid structure from bio-inks. The process should be fast and non-toxic to cells.
3. Biocompatibility: Natural bio-inks can't endure harsh conditions. On the other hand, although synthetic bio-inks are applicable to large production capacity, they do not provide cell adhesion sites.
4. Living cells can sense their environments movements and there for can change their behavior. Accordingly, by considering mechanical parameters of bio-inks we can control modifications of cell behaviors (Ramadan and Zourob 2021).

Antibacterial composites, in particular, have been a focus of recent research, as they offer a potential solution to the ongoing issue of bacterial or viral infection (like corona virus) in medical devices (Anon n.d.-g). 3D printing allows for the precise control of material composition and structure, enabling the creation of antibacterial composites that have unique mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties. These composites can be tailored to specific applications, such as retentive medicine and wearable sensors, to provide improved performance and long-lasting protection against bacterial infection (Hospodiuk et al., 2017; Leppiniemi et al., 2017). 3D printed antibacterial composites offer the potential to improve the efficacy and safety of retentive medicine by providing a barrier against bacterial colonization and reducing the risk of infection. Wearable sensors, such as fitness trackers and smartwatches, are increasingly popular due to their convenience and ability to monitor health data in real-time. However, the close proximity of these devices to the skin presents a risk of bacterial infection. 3D printed antibacterial composites can be used to produce wearable

sensors that are not only functional but also safe and hygienic. Accordingly, bacteria after adhesion to the surface of 3D printed composite, was killed (Yue et al., 2015).

In order to control and modify the physical and chemical characteristics of polymeric systems, like flow behavior, stiffness, swelling, decomposition, and function of the produced materials, nano-clay has been added to these systems. When nano-clay is added to polymers, the solution may develop an internal structure that allows for shear-thinning qualities and enhanced recoverability without damaging the molecular structure. One of the most popular clay based hydrogels printed with 3D printing is addition of nano-clay to polymeric solutions (PEG–alginate) mimic the properties of soft tissue (Hong et al., 2015). On the other hand, in alginate-based 3D printed material face collapses and shape fidelities. In this way cellulose is an alluring component to overcome these limitations by rheological modifying and improving mechanical properties (Gutierrez et al., 2019). Moreover, Figure 7 shows usage of carboxymethyl cellulose as bio ink in 3D printing and preparation of wound healing scaffold.

Figure 6. 3D bio-printing process in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine (Azman, 2022).

Figure 7. Example of utilizing cellulose in scaffolds with 3D printing. Adapted from (Wei et al., 2020; Anon. n.d.-j.).

FUTURE EXPECTATIONS

Wearable sensors and sensor technology have been advancing at an unprecedented pace, with innovations that continue to shape and redefine the possibilities of healthcare, fitness, and overall wellness. The global market for wearable sensors is expected to grow significantly in the coming years, driven by a combination of factors, including the increasing demand for personalized healthcare solutions, rising prevalence of chronic diseases, and the growing awareness about health and fitness (Andreu-Perez et al., 2015).

Another promising area of development in wearable sensors is the integration of machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms, which can provide more accurate and personalized insights into an individual's health and fitness. By analyzing data collected from wearable sensors, machine learning algorithms can identify patterns and trends that can help predict potential health issues, and provide tailored recommendations for better health outcomes (Junaid et al., 2022; Shan et al., 2020).

In addition, wearable sensors are becoming more sophisticated and specialized, with sensors designed for specific applications such as sports training, sleep monitoring, and stress management. For example, wearable sensors that can track an athlete's performance, monitor their progress, and detect early signs of injury can help optimize training and prevent injuries (Seshadri et al., 2019).

However, there are still several challenges that need to be addressed before wearable sensors can fully realize their potential. For example, ensuring data privacy and security is a major concern, as wearable sensors collect sensitive health information that needs to be protected. Furthermore, there is a need for more standardization and interoperability in wearable sensor technology to ensure seamless integration and communication between different devices. In conclusion, wearable sensors and sensor technology have enormous potential to transform healthcare, fitness, and overall wellbeing. With ongoing advancements and innovations in the field, the future of wearable sensors looks promising, and we can expect to see even more sophisticated and specialized devices that can provide personalized health insights and improve overall health outcomes.

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REFERENCES

- Abdelkhalek, Ahmed, and Abdulaziz A. Al-Askar. 2020. "Green Synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles Mediated by Mentha Spicata Extract Induce Plant Systemic Resistance against Tobacco Mosaic Virus." *Applied Sciences* 10(15):5054. doi: 10.3390/app10155054.
- Abdul Majid, M. S., Mohd Ridzuan Mohd Jamir, and K. H. Lim. 2020. "Effect of Nanoclay Filler on Mechanical and Morphological Properties of Napier/ Epoxy Composites." Pp. 137–62 in.
- Abomuti, May Abdullah, Ekram Y. Danish, Ahmad Firoz, Nazim Hasan, and Maqsood Ahmad Malik. 2021. "Green Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles Using Salvia Officinalis Leaf Extract and Their Photocatalytic and Antifungal Activities." *Biology* 10(11):1075. doi: 10.3390/biology10111075.
- Abou-Yousef, Hussein, Sawsan Dacrory, Mohamed Hasanin, Essam Saber, and Samir Kamel. 2021. "Biocompatible Hydrogel Based on Aldehyde-Functionalized Cellulose and Chitosan for

Potential Control Drug Release.” *Sustainable Chemistry and Pharmacy* 21:100419. doi: 10.1016/j.scp.2021.100419.

Ahmad, Mohammad Zaki, Ali S. Alasiri, Javed Ahmad, Abdulsalam A. Alqahtani, Md Margub Abdullah, Basel A. Abdel-Wahab, Kalyani Pathak, Riya Saikia, Aparoop Das, Himangshu Sarma, and Seham Abdullah Alzahrani. 2022. “Green Synthesis of Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles Using *Ocimum Sanctum* Leaf Extract: In Vitro Characterization and Its Healing Efficacy in Diabetic Wounds.” *Molecules* 27(22):7712. doi: 10.3390/molecules27227712.

Andreu-Perez, Javier, Daniel R. Leff, H. M. D. Ip, and Guang-Zhong Yang. 2015. “From Wearable Sensors to Smart Implants—Toward Pervasive and Personalized Healthcare.” *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 62(12):2750–62. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2015.2422751.

Anju, T. R., S. Parvathy, Mohanan Valiya Veetil, J. Rosemary, T. H. Ansalna, M. M. Shahzabanu, and S. Devika. 2021. “Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles from Aloe Vera Leaf Extract and Its Antimicrobial Activity.” *Materials Today: Proceedings* 43:3956–60. doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.02.665.

Anon. n.d.-a. “Copper–Cellulose Complexes | Nature.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (<https://www.nature.com/articles/183988a0>).

Anon. n.d.-b. “Full Article: Biogenesis of Copper Nanoparticles Using Peel Extract of *Punica Granatum* and Their Antimicrobial Activity against Opportunistic Pathogens.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17518253.2016.1141238>).

Anon. n.d.-c. “Full Article: Microwave-Irradiated Green Synthesis of Metallic Silver and Copper Nanoparticles Using Fresh Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) Rhizome Extract and Evaluation of Their Antibacterial Potentials and Cytotoxicity.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/24701556.2020.1808017?casa_token=ThDj19IYKA8AAAAA%3AvXS8SNo_V5sq2Z9M5IvCwm8D6Cnx9KYcCJ2TG1aZrgx3LFvEnBwLKVwhut37zX0CvYsqRdFBwG5TSQ).

Anon. n.d.-d. “Green Synthesis of Palladium Nanoparticles Using Broth of *Cinnamomum Camphora* Leaf | SpringerLink.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11051-009-9675-1>).

Anon. n.d.-e. “Nanocellulose as Sustainable Biomaterials for Drug Delivery | Elsevier Enhanced Reader.” Retrieved November 15, 2022 (<https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S2666351121000565?token=8FE9BB5EAA676A05541FCB66EB89306720F0992DC893C256B65A091B2730E9BD944598DB86BDDC83EEAC0F84AC9488B6&originRegion=eu-west-1&originCreation=20221115114233>).

Anon. n.d.-f. “Nanocellulose toward Advanced Energy Storage Devices: Structure and Electrochemistry | Accounts of Chemical Research.” Retrieved January 6, 2023 (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/full/10.1021/acs.accounts.8b00391>).

Anon. n.d.-g. “Novel Antimicrobial Materials Designed for the 3D Printing of Medical Devices Used during the COVID-19 Crisis | Emerald Insight.” Retrieved February 10, 2023 (<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/RPJ-09-2020-0219/full/html>).

Anon. n.d.-h. “Rapid Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles by Waste Thyme (*Thymus Vulgaris* L.) | SpringerLink.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13762-018-2112-1>).

Anon. n.d.-i. “The Green Synthesis of MgO Nano-Flowers Using *Rosmarinus Officinalis* L. (Rosemary) and the Antibacterial Activities against *Xanthomonas Oryzae* Pv. *Oryzae*.” Retrieved February 7, 2023 (<https://www.hindawi.com/journals/bmri/2019/5620989/>).

Anon. n.d.-j. “The Use of Cellulose in Bio-Derived Formulations for 3D/4D Printing: A Review | Elsevier Enhanced Reader.” Retrieved October 13, 2022 (<https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S2666682021000086?token=C080571E36439ECC8F8149ADA45D3AE4C13D5E4CE08F792E0E47D49A3FF6084195ADB96D980A6BEB041E8CFD50EEF54D&originRegion=eu-west-1&originCreation=20221013125647>).

Ansari, Mohammad Azam, Mahadevamurthy Murali, Daruka Prasad, Mohammad A. Alzohairy, Ahmad Almatroudi, Mohammad N. Alomary, Arakere Chunchegowda Udayashankar, Sudarshana Brijesh Singh, Sarah Mousa Maadi Asiri, Bagepalli Shivaram Ashwini, Hittanahallikoppal Gajendramurthy Gowtham, Nataraj Kalegowda, Kestur Nagaraj Amruthesh, Thimappa Ramachandrappa Lakshmeesha, and Siddapura Ramachandrappa Niranjana. 2020. “Cinnamomum Verum Bark Extract Mediated Green Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles and Their Antibacterial Potentiality.” *Biomolecules* 10(2):336. doi: 10.3390/biom10020336.

Armentano, I., N. Bitinis, E. Fortunati, S. Mattioli, N. Rescignano, R. Verdejo, M. A. Lopez-Manchado, and J. M. Kenny. 2013. “Multifunctional Nanostructured PLA Materials for Packaging and Tissue Engineering.” *Progress in Polymer Science* 38(10):1720–47. doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2013.05.010.

Ashrafi, Ghazaleh, Mahmoud Nasrollahzadeh, Babak Jaleh, Mohaddeseh Sajjadi, and Hossein Ghafari. 2022. “Biowaste- and Nature-Derived (Nano)Materials: Biosynthesis, Stability and Environmental Applications.” *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* 301:102599. doi: 10.1016/j.cis.2022.102599.

Bahloul, Adil, Zineb Kassab, Mehdi El Bouchti, Hassan Hannache, Abou El Kacem Qaiss, Mina Oumam, and Mounir El Achaby. 2021. “Micro- and Nano-Structures of Cellulose from Eggplant Plant (*Solanum Melongena* L) Agricultural Residue.” *Carbohydrate Polymers* 253:117311. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2020.117311.

Barakan, Shima, and Valeh Aghazadeh. 2021. “The Advantages of Clay Mineral Modification Methods for Enhancing Adsorption Efficiency in Wastewater Treatment: A Review.” *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 28(3):2572–99. doi: 10.1007/s11356-020-10985-9.

Baruah, Kakali, Mahabul Haque, Leader Langbang, Sourav Das, Kripamoy Aguan, and Atanu Singha Roy. 2021. “Ocimum Sanctum Mediated Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles: A Biophysical Study towards Lysozyme Binding and Anti-Bacterial Activity.” *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 337:116422. doi: 10.1016/j.molliq.2021.116422.

Benli, B., F. Boylu, M. F. Can, F. Karakaş, K. Çinku, and G. Ersever. 2011. “Rheological, Electrokinetic, and Morphological Characterization of Alginate–Bentonite Biocomposites.” *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 122(1):19–28. doi: 10.1002/app.33627.

Benli, Birgül, and Ecehan Gönül. 2021. “Functionalized Sepiolitic Clay Nanofibers as a Natural Ingredient in Medical Cosmetics.” *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society Section A: Chemistry* 8(2):471–76. doi: 10.18596/jotcsa.847163.

Benli, Birgul, and Cansu Yalın. 2017. “The Influence of Silver and Copper Ions on the Antibacterial Activity and Local Electrical Properties of Single Sepiolite Fiber: A Conductive Atomic Force Microscopy (C-AFM) Study.” *Applied Clay Science* 146:449–56. doi: 10.1016/j.clay.2017.06.024.

Bergaya, F., and G. Lagaly. 2006. “Chapter 1 General Introduction: Clays, Clay Minerals, and Clay Science.” Pp. 1–18 in *Developments in Clay Science*. Vol. 1, *Handbook of Clay Science*, edited by Faïza Bergaya, B. K. G. Theng, and Gerhard Lagaly. Elsevier.

Brigatti, M. F., C. Lugli, and L. Poppi. 2000. “Kinetics of Heavy-Metal Removal and Recovery in Sepiolite.” *Applied Clay Science* 16(1):45–57. doi: 10.1016/S0169-1317(99)00046-0.

- Choudhary, Manoj Kumar, Jyoti Kataria, and Shweta Sharma. 2018. "Evaluation of the Kinetic and Catalytic Properties of Biogenically Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 198:882–90. doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.015.
- Choudhury, Hira, Manisha Pandey, Yan Qing Lim, Chea Yee Low, Cheng Teck Lee, Tee Cheng Ling Marilyn, Huai Seang Loh, Yee Ping Lim, Cheng Feng Lee, Subrat Kumar Bhattamishra, Prashant Kesharwani, and Bapi Gorain. 2020. "Silver Nanoparticles: Advanced and Promising Technology in Diabetic Wound Therapy." *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 112:110925. doi: 10.1016/j.msec.2020.110925.
- Daruich De Souza, Carla, Beatriz Ribeiro Nogueira, and Maria Elisa C. M. Rostelato. 2019. "Review of the Methodologies Used in the Synthesis Gold Nanoparticles by Chemical Reduction." *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 798:714–40. doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.05.153.
- Demirci, Selami, Zeynep Ustaoglu, Gonca Altın Yilmazer, Fikretin Sahin, and Nurcan Baç. 2014. "Antimicrobial Properties of Zeolite-X and Zeolite-A Ion-Exchanged with Silver, Copper, and Zinc Against a Broad Range of Microorganisms." *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology* 172(3):1652–62. doi: 10.1007/s12010-013-0647-7.
- Elsamra, Rehab M. I., Mamdouh S. Masoud, Alyaa A. Zidan, Gehan M. El Zokm, and Mohamed A. Okbah. 2023. "Green Synthesis of Nanostructured Zinc Oxide by Ocimum Tenuiflorum Extract: Characterization, Adsorption Modeling, Cytotoxic Screening, and Metal Ions Adsorption Applications." *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. doi: 10.1007/s13399-022-03709-1.
- Ertas Onmaz, Nurhan, Dilek Demirezen Yilmaz, Kálmán Imre, Adriana Morar, Candan Gungor, Seyda Yilmaz, Dursun Alp Gundog, Adalet Dishan, Viorel Herman, and Guven Gungor. 2022. "Green Synthesis of Gold Nanoflowers Using Rosmarinus Officinalis and Helichrysum Italicum Extracts: Comparative Studies of Their Antimicrobial and Antibiofilm Activities." *Antibiotics* 11(11):1466. doi: 10.3390/antibiotics11111466.
- Fatema, M., Alkfaji, Ibtihal Al Hussaini, and Al Hussaini. 2021. "Biosynthesis of Silver Nanoparticles with Mentha Spicata against Aspergillus Niger." *Drug Invention Today* 14.
- Friedrich, Ralf P., Iwona Cicha, and Christoph Alexiou. 2021a. "Iron Oxide Nanoparticles in Regenerative Medicine and Tissue Engineering." *Nanomaterials* 11(9):2337. doi: 10.3390/nano11092337.
- Friedrich, Ralf P., Iwona Cicha, and Christoph Alexiou. 2021b. "Iron Oxide Nanoparticles in Regenerative Medicine and Tissue Engineering." *Nanomaterials* 11(9):2337. doi: 10.3390/nano11092337.
- Fu, Xaoan, and Syed Qutubuddin. 2000. "Synthesis of Polystyrene–Clay Nanocomposites." *Materials Letters* 42(1):12–15. doi: 10.1016/S0167-577X(99)00151-2.
- Gabrielli, Valeria, and Marco Frascioni. 2022. "Cellulose-Based Functional Materials for Sensing." *Chemosensors* 10(9):352. doi: 10.3390/chemosensors10090352.
- Günister, Ebru, Dilay Pestreli, Cüneyt H. Ünlü, Oya Atıcı, and Nurfer Güngör. 2007. "Synthesis and Characterization of Chitosan-MMT Biocomposite Systems." *Carbohydrate Polymers* 67(3):358–65. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2006.06.004.
- Gutierrez, Elena, Patricio A. Burdiles, Franck Quero, Patricia Palma, Felipe Olate-Moya, and Humberto Palza. 2019. "3D Printing of Antimicrobial Alginate/Bacterial-Cellulose Composite Hydrogels by Incorporating Copper Nanostructures." *ACS Biomaterials Science & Engineering* 5(11):6290–99. doi: 10.1021/acsbiomaterials.9b01048.
- Guzman, Maribel, Jean Dille, and Stéphane Godet. 2012. "Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Silver Nanoparticles against Gram-Positive and Gram-Negative Bacteria." *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine* 8(1):37–45. doi: 10.1016/j.nano.2011.05.007.

- Hasanin, Mohamed S. 2022. "Cellulose-Based Biomaterials: Chemistry and Biomedical Applications." *Starch - Stärke* 74(7–8):2200060. doi: 10.1002/star.202200060.
- Helios-Rybacka, E. 1985. "Sorption of Ni, Zn and Cd on Sepiolite." *Clay Minerals* 20(4):525–27. doi: 10.1180/claymin.1985.020.4.09.
- Hong, Sungmin, Dalton Sycks, Hon Fai Chan, Shaoting Lin, Gabriel P. Lopez, Farshid Guilak, Kam W. Leong, and Xuanhe Zhao. 2015. "3D Printing of Highly Stretchable and Tough Hydrogels into Complex, Cellularized Structures." *Advanced Materials* 27(27):4035–40. doi: 10.1002/adma.201501099.
- Hospodiuk, Monika, Madhuri Dey, Donna Sosnoski, and Ibrahim T. Ozbolat. 2017. "The Bioink: A Comprehensive Review on Bioprintable Materials." *Biotechnology Advances* 35(2):217–39. doi: 10.1016/j.biotechadv.2016.12.006.
- Hu, Daihua, Tingting Gao, Xingang Kong, Na Ma, Jinhong Fu, Lina Meng, Xiaolong Duan, Ching Yuan Hu, Wang Chen, Zili Feng, and Salman Latif. 2022. "Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) Extract Mediated Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles and Evaluation of Their Antioxidant Activity and Potential Catalytic Reduction Activities with Direct Blue 15 or Direct Orange 26." *PLOS ONE* 17(8):e0271408. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0271408.
- Iqbal, Yasir, Abdul Raouf Malik, Tanzeel Iqbal, Muhammad Hammad Aziz, Faisal Ahmed, Fouad A. Abolaban, Syed Mansoor Ali, and Hafeez Ullah. 2021. "Green Synthesis of ZnO and Ag-Doped ZnO Nanoparticles Using *Azadirachta Indica* Leaves: Characterization and Their Potential Antibacterial, Antidiabetic, and Wound-Healing Activities." *Materials Letters* 305:130671. doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2021.130671.
- Janaswamy, Srinivas, Madhav P. Yadav, Mominul Hoque, Sajal Bhattarai, and Shafaet Ahmed. 2022. "Cellulosic Fraction from Agricultural Biomass as a Viable Alternative for Plastics and Plastic Products." *Industrial Crops and Products* 179:114692. doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.114692.
- Junaid, Sahalu Balarabe, Abdullahi Abubakar Imam, Muhammad Abdulkarim, Yusuf Alhaji Surakat, Abdullateef Oluwagbemiga Balogun, Ganesh Kumar, Aliyu Nuhu Shuaibu, Aliyu Garba, Yusra Sahalu, Abdullahi Mohammed, Tanko Yahaya Mohammed, Bashir Abubakar Abdulkadir, Abdallah Alkali Abba, Nana Aliyu Iliyasu Kakumi, and Ahmad Sobri Hashim. 2022. "Recent Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Wearable Sensors in Healthcare Delivery." *Applied Sciences* 12(20):10271. doi: 10.3390/app122010271.
- Kaliamurthi, Satyavani, Gurudeeban Selvaraj, Ramanathan, and Balasubramanian Thangavel. 2013. "Ipomoea Pes-Caprae Mediated Silver Nanoparticles and Their Antibacterial Effect." *Science International* 1:155–59. doi: 10.5567/sciintl.2013.155.159.
- Kamel, Samir, and Tawfik A. Khattab. 2020. "Recent Advances in Cellulose-Based Biosensors for Medical Diagnosis." *Biosensors* 10(6):67. doi: 10.3390/bios10060067.
- Kamran, Urooj, Haq Nawaz Bhatti, Munawar Iqbal, Saba Jamil, and Muhammad Zahid. 2019. "Biogenic Synthesis, Characterization and Investigation of Photocatalytic and Antimicrobial Activity of Manganese Nanoparticles Synthesized from *Cinnamomum Verum* Bark Extract." *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1179:532–39. doi: 10.1016/j.molstruc.2018.11.006.
- Kara, M., H. Yuzer, E. Sabah, and M. S. Celik. 2003. "Adsorption of Cobalt from Aqueous Solutions onto Sepiolite." *Water Research* 37(1):224–32. doi: 10.1016/S0043-1354(02)00265-8.
- Komadel, P., and J. Madejová. 2006. "Chapter 7.1 Acid Activation of Clay Minerals." Pp. 263–87 in *Developments in Clay Science*. Vol. 1, *Handbook of Clay Science*, edited by F. Bergaya, B. K. G. Theng, and G. Lagaly. Elsevier.
- Leppiniemi, Jenni, Panu Lahtinen, Antti Paajanen, Riitta Mahlberg, Sini Metsä-Kortelainen, Tatu Pinomaa, Heikki Pajari, Inger Vikholm-Lundin, Pekka Pursula, and Vesa P. Hytönen. 2017. "3D-

- Printable Bioactivated Nanocellulose–Alginate Hydrogels.” *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 9(26):21959–70. doi: 10.1021/acsami.7b02756.
- Lin, Ning, and Alain Dufresne. 2014. “Nanocellulose in Biomedicine: Current Status and Future Prospect.” *European Polymer Journal* 59:302–25. doi: 10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2014.07.025.
- Ling, Shengjie, Wenshuai Chen, Yimin Fan, Ke Zheng, Kai Jin, Haipeng Yu, Markus J. Buehler, and David L. Kaplan. 2018. “Biopolymer Nanofibrils: Structure, Modeling, Preparation, and Applications.” *Progress in Polymer Science* 85:1–56. doi: 10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2018.06.004.
- Luque, Rafael, and Rajender S. Varma. 2012. *Sustainable Preparation of Metal Nanoparticles: Methods and Applications*. Royal Society of Chemistry.
- Mallakpour, Shadpour, Maryam Tukhani, and Chaudhery Mustansar Hussain. 2021. “Recent Advancements in 3D Bioprinting Technology of Carboxymethyl Cellulose-Based Hydrogels: Utilization in Tissue Engineering.” *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* 292:102415. doi: 10.1016/j.cis.2021.102415.
- Mateo, Soledad, Silvia Peinado, Francisca Morillas-Gutiérrez, M. Dolores La Rubia, and Alberto J. Moya. 2021. “Nanocellulose from Agricultural Wastes: Products and Applications—A Review.” *Processes* 9(9):1594. doi: 10.3390/pr9091594.
- Mohd Zuki, S. A., N. Abd Rahman, and N. F. Abu Bakar. 2018. “Nanocrystal Cellulose as Drug Excipient in Transdermal Patch for Wound Healing: An Overview.” *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 334:012046. doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/334/1/012046.
- Nasrollahzadeh, Mahmoud, Mohaddeseh Sajjadi, Siavash Irvani, and Rajender Varma. 2021. “Starch, Cellulose, Pectin, Gum, Alginate, Chitin and Chitosan Derived (Nano)Materials for Sustainable Water Treatment: A Review.” *Carbohydrate Polymers* 251. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2020.116986.
- Nurul Azman, Mohamad. 2022. “Biopolymers and Sustainable Biopolymer-Based Composites: Fabrication, Failure, and Repairing.” Pp. 27–37 in.
- Palanisamy, Navindra Kumari, Nas Ferina, Athirah Nur Amirulhusni, Zaini Mohd-Zain, Jamal Hussaini, Liew Jian Ping, and Rajkumar Durairaj. 2014. “Antibiofilm Properties of Chemically Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles Found against *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*.” *Journal of Nanobiotechnology* 12(1):2. doi: 10.1186/1477-3155-12-2.
- Piantanida, Etienne, Giuseppe Alonci, Alessandro Bertucci, and Luisa De Cola. 2019. “Design of Nanocomposite Injectable Hydrogels for Minimally Invasive Surgery.” *Accounts of Chemical Research* 52(8):2101–12. doi: 10.1021/acs.accounts.9b00114.
- Pourmortazavi, Seied Mahdi, Mehdi Taghdiri, Vajihe Makari, and Mehdi Rahimi-Nasrabadi. 2015. “Procedure Optimization for Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles by Aqueous Extract of *Eucalyptus Oleosa*.” *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy* 136:1249–54. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2014.10.010.
- R. Tamileswari, M. Haniff Nisha, Sr. S. Jesurani, and Jayaraj Annapackiam college for women(Autonomous). 2015. “Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Using Brassica Oleracea (Cauliflower) and Brassica Oleracea Capitata (Cabbage) and the Analysis of Antimicrobial Activity.” *International Journal of Engineering Research And* V4(04):IJERTV4IS041196. doi: 10.17577/IJERTV4IS041196.
- Ramadan, Qasem, and Mohammed Zourob. 2021. “3D Bioprinting at the Frontier of Regenerative Medicine, Pharmaceutical, and Food Industries.” *Frontiers in Medical Technology* 2.
- Same, Saeideh, Sattar Akbari Nakhjavani, Golshan Samee, Golnaz Navidi, Yalda jahanbani, and Soodabeh Davaran. 2022. “Halloysite Clay Nanotube in Regenerative Medicine for Tissue and Wound Healing.” *Ceramics International* 48(21):31065–79. doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.05.037.

- Seddiqi, Hadi, Erfan Oliaei, Hengameh Honarkar, Jianfeng Jin, Lester C. Geonzon, Rommel G. Bacabac, and Jenneke Klein-Nulend. 2021. "Cellulose and Its Derivatives: Towards Biomedical Applications." *Cellulose* 28(4):1893–1931. doi: 10.1007/s10570-020-03674-w.
- Sehnal, Karel, Bozena Hosnedlova, Michaela Docekalova, Martina Stankova, Dagmar Uhlirova, Zuzana Tothova, Marta Kepinska, Halina Milnerowicz, Carlos Fernandez, Branislav Ruttkay-Nedecky, Hoai Viet Nguyen, Augustine Ofomaja, Jiri Sochor, and Rene Kizek. 2019. "An Assessment of the Effect of Green Synthesized Silver Nanoparticles Using Sage Leaves (*Salvia Officinalis* L.) on Germinated Plants of Maize (*Zea Mays* L.)." *Nanomaterials* 9(11):1550. doi: 10.3390/nano9111550.
- Seshadri, Dhruv R., Ryan T. Li, James E. Voos, James R. Rowbottom, Celeste M. Alfes, Christian A. Zorman, and Colin K. Drummond. 2019. "Wearable Sensors for Monitoring the Internal and External Workload of the Athlete." *Npj Digital Medicine* 2(1):1–18. doi: 10.1038/s41746-019-0149-2.
- Shan, Guangcun, Xin Li, and Wei Huang. 2020. "AI-Enabled Wearable and Flexible Electronics for Assessing Full Personal Exposures." *The Innovation* 1(2):100031. doi: 10.1016/j.xinn.2020.100031.
- Sheikh, Faheem A., Nasser A. M. Barakat, Muzafar A. Kanjwal, Atul A. Chaudhari, In-Hee Jung, John Hwa Lee, and Hak Yong Kim. 2009. "Electrospun Antimicrobial Polyurethane Nanofibers Containing Silver Nanoparticles for Biotechnological Applications." *Macromolecular Research* 17(9):688–96. doi: 10.1007/BF03218929.
- Singer, Arie, Emilio Galán Huertos, and Emilio Galan. 2011. *Developments in Palygorskite-Sepiolite Research: A New Outlook on These Nanomaterials*. Elsevier.
- Spagnuolo, Laura, Rosarita D’Orsi, and Alessandra Operamolla. 2022. "Nanocellulose for Paper and Textile Coating: The Importance of Surface Chemistry." *ChemPlusChem* 87(8):e202200204. doi: 10.1002/cplu.202200204.
- Trache, Djalal. 2018. "Nanocellulose as a Promising Sustainable Material for Biomedical Applications." *AIMS Materials Science (2372-0484)* 5:201–5. doi: 10.3934/matserci.2018.2.201.
- Umair Wani, Taha, Anjum Hamid Rather, Rumysa Saleem Khan, Javier Macossay, Arvind H. Jadhav, Puneethkumar M. Srinivasappa, Abdalla Abdal-hay, Sami-ullah Rather, and Faheem A. Sheikh. 2023. "Titanium Dioxide Functionalized Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes and Silver Nanoparticles Reinforced Polyurethane Nanofibers as a Novel Scaffold for Tissue Engineering Applications." *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*. doi: 10.1016/j.jiec.2023.01.024.
- Venkatadri, B., E. Shanparvish, M. R. Rameshkumar, Mariadhas Valan Arasu, Naif Abdullah Al-Dhabi, Vinoth Kumar Ponnusamy, and P. Agastian. 2020. "Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles Using Aqueous Rhizome Extract of *Zingiber Officinale* and *Curcuma Longa*: In-Vitro Anti-Cancer Potential on Human Colon Carcinoma HT-29 Cells." *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 27(11):2980–86. doi: 10.1016/j.sjbs.2020.09.021.
- Vicente, M. A., A. Gil, and F. Bergaya. 2013. "Chapter 10.5 - Pillared Clays and Clay Minerals." Pp. 523–57 in *Developments in Clay Science*. Vol. 5, *Handbook of Clay Science*, edited by Faïza Bergaya and G. Lagaly. Elsevier.
- Vignesh, N., K. Chandraraj, S. P. Suriyaraj, and R. Selvakumar. 2022. "Cellulose – A Sustainable Material for Biomedical Applications." in *Advanced Materials for Biomechanical Applications*. CRC Press.
- Villanueva, M. P., L. Cabedo, E. Giménez, J. M. Lagarón, P. D. Coates, and A. L. Kelly. 2009. "Study of the Dispersion of Nanoclays in a LDPE Matrix Using Microscopy and In-Process Ultrasonic Monitoring." *Polymer Testing* 28(3):277–87. doi: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2008.12.009.

Vinicius de Oliveira Brisola Maciel, Matheus, Aline da Rosa Almeida, Michelle Heck Machado, Welman Curi Elias, Cleonice Gonçalves da Rosa, Gerson Lopes Teixeira, Carolina Montanheiro Noronha, Fabiano Cleber Bertoldi, Michael Ramos Nunes, Rafael Dutra de Armas, and Pedro Luiz Manique Barreto. 2020. “Green Synthesis, Characteristics and Antimicrobial Activity of Silver Nanoparticles Mediated by Essential Oils as Reducing Agents.” *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology* 28:101746. doi: 10.1016/j.bcab.2020.101746.

Vyavahare, Sachin, Nitin Padole, and Jasmine Avari. 2021. “A REVIEW: SILVER NANOPARTICLES IN WOUND HEALING.” *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH* 8:212–18.

Wang, Chunya, Kailun Xia, Yingying Zhang, and David L. Kaplan. 2019. “Silk-Based Advanced Materials for Soft Electronics.” *Accounts of Chemical Research* 52(10):2916–27. doi: 10.1021/acs.accounts.9b00333.

Wei, Jiaxin, Baoxiu Wang, Zhe Li, Zhuotong Wu, Minghao Zhang, Nan Sheng, Qianqian Liang, Huaping Wang, and Shiyan Chen. 2020. “A 3D-Printable TEMPO-Oxidized Bacterial Cellulose/Alginate Hydrogel with Enhanced Stability via Nanoclay Incorporation.” *Carbohydrate Polymers* 238:116207. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2020.116207.

Yang, Guang, Jianjian Xie, Yunxia Deng, Yonggang Bian, and Feng Hong. 2012. “Hydrothermal Synthesis of Bacterial Cellulose/AgNPs Composite: A ‘Green’ Route for Antibacterial Application.” *Carbohydrate Polymers* 87(4):2482–87. doi: 10.1016/j.carbpol.2011.11.017.

Yue, Jun, Pei Zhao, Jennifer Y. Gerasimov, Marieke van de Lagemaat, Arjen Grotenhuis, Minie Rustema-Abbing, Henny C. van der Mei, Henk J. Busscher, Andreas Herrmann, and Yijin Ren. 2015. “3D-Printable Antimicrobial Composite Resins.” *Advanced Functional Materials* 25(43):6756–67. doi: 10.1002/adfm.201502384.

Zhou, Shengyang, Leif Nyholm, Maria Strømme, and Zhaohui Wang. 2019. “Cladophora Cellulose: Unique Biopolymer Nanofibrils for Emerging Energy, Environmental, and Life Science Applications.” *Accounts of Chemical Research* 52(8):2232–43. doi: 10.1021/acs.accounts.9b00215.